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PROMISING DIRECTIONS FOR APPLYING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of green tourism development in Uzbekistan, along with a comprehensive review of advanced international practices. In particular, the approaches of Costa Rica, Slovenia, Bhutan, New Zealand, and Germany to sustainable tourism development are examined. The study places special emphasis on national "green brand" systems, environmental certification mechanisms, environmental protection funds, and community-based management models. Furthermore, the article identifies promising directions for adapting international experiences to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Green tourism in Uzbekistan, sustainable tourism, international experience, ecotourism, certification system, community participation, environmental policy, tourism infrastructure, sustainable development.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda yashil turizmni rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari hamda xorijiy mamlakatlarning ilg'or tajribalari kompleks tarzda tahlil etilgan. Jumladan, Costa Rica, Sloveniya, Bhutan, Yangi Zelandiya va Germaniya davlatlarining barqaror turizmni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan yondashuvlari o'rganildi. Tadqiqot jarayonida, ayniqsa, milliy "green brand" tizimlari, ekologik sertifikatlash mexanizmlari, atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish jamg'armalari hamda jamoatchilik ishtirokiga asoslangan boshqaruv modellari tahlil qilindi. Maqolada xorijiy tajribalarni O'zbekiston sharoitiga moslashtirishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari aniqlab berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekistonda yashil turizm, barqaror turizm, xorijiy tajriba, ekoturizm, sertifikatlash tizimi, mahalliy jamoa ishtiroki, ekologik siyosat, turizm infratuzilmasi, barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В данной статье комплексно проанализированы теоретико-методологические основы развития зелёного туризма в Узбекистане, а также передовой опыт зарубежных стран. В частности, изучены подходы таких государств, как Costa Rica, Sloveniya, Bhutan, Yangi Zelandiya и Germaniya, направленные на развитие устойчивого туризма. В ходе исследования особое внимание уделено национальным системам «green brand», механизмам экологической сертификации, фондам охраны окружающей среды, а также моделям управления, основанным на участии общественности. В статье определены перспективные направления адаптации зарубежного опыта к условиям Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: зелёный туризм в Узбекистане, устойчивый туризм, зарубежный опыт, экотуризм, система сертификации, участие местного сообщества, экологическая политика, туристическая инфраструктура, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, alongside the growing economic significance of tourism, increasing global attention has been directed toward its environmental, social, and cultural impacts. The concept of "green tourism" (also referred to as sustainable tourism) is oriented toward environmental conservation, the support of local communities, and

the promotion of long-term economic sustainability. Uzbekistan's rich historical heritage, diverse natural zones, and newly emerging tourist routes create substantial opportunities for the development of green tourism. At the same time, the effective and widespread implementation of green tourism in the country requires coherent state policies, the efficient utilization of local resources, well-defined environmental standards, and strong motivation within the private sector.

The "Strategy for the Transition to a Green Economy," adopted in 2019 by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, serves as a key strategic document aimed at ensuring the country's sustainable development and promoting the advancement of green tourism¹.

The implementation of the tasks outlined in the Presidential Decree No. PF-158 of September 11, 2023, "On the Strategy 'Uzbekistan – 2030'," as well as the Presidential Resolution No. PQ-436 of December 2, 2022, "On measures to enhance the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a 'Green' Economy by 2030," along with other regulatory and legal documents, contributes to improving public awareness and literacy in the field of green tourism in Uzbekistan².

The aim of this article is to analyze the successful experiences of foreign countries in the field of green/sustainable tourism, to identify the prospects for their application in Uzbekistan, and to develop practical recommendations. The study examines specific programs and mechanisms implemented in countries such as Costa Rica, Slovenia, Bhutan, New Zealand, and Germany, and proposes ways of adapting these practices to the conditions of Uzbekistan. Furthermore, based on relevant policy documents and research studies, the article briefly presents the current situation and existing opportunities within the country (for instance, recent studies and analyses indicate the presence of sustainability-related challenges in Uzbekistan's tourism sector)³.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The theoretical aspects of green tourism development have been addressed by a number of scholars in their academic research.

Green tourism is defined as a form of tourism that operates without causing harm to natural and ecological systems, while generating positive outcomes for local communities and economies. It requires the rational and efficient use of water, energy, and other resources⁴.

"The concept of sustainable tourism implies that tourism development must be balanced across economic, social, and environmental dimensions. At the same time, it is essential to preserve natural and cultural resources for future generations⁵".

"The key factor in the development of green tourism is the collaboration between government authorities and local communities in tourism management, as well as the strict implementation of environmental standards⁶".

"The development of sustainable tourism, particularly green tourism, contributes not only to the conservation of natural resources but also to the enhancement of the social and economic well-being of local populations⁷".

"The development of green tourism is achieved through the implementation of innovative technologies, the improvement of energy efficiency, and the reduction of waste. This approach not only ensures environmental sustainability but also enhances the competitiveness of the tourism sector⁸".

"The core principle of green and sustainable tourism is to preserve natural and cultural heritage, minimize the environmental impact of tourism services, and contribute positively to the local economy⁹".

Based on the opinions of scholars and researchers, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Green tourism is an important tool for sustainable development, requiring the conservation of ecological systems and the rational use of natural resources.
- The concept of sustainable tourism integrates social, economic, and environmental criteria, thereby contributing to the preservation of resources for future generations.
- The effective development of green tourism is ensured through collaboration between local communities and government authorities, strict enforcement of environmental standards, and the adoption of innovative technologies.

1 <https://lex.uz/docs/-4539502>

2 <https://lex.uz/docs/-6303230>

3 <https://www.visitcostarica.com/sustainability>

4 Gössling, S., Scott, D., Hall, C.M. *Tourism and Water: Interactions, Impacts and Challenges*. – Bristol: Channel View Publications, 2015.

5 Weaver, D. *Sustainable Tourism: Theory and Practice*. – Oxford: Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann, 2006.

6 Bramwell, B., Lane, B. *Critical research on the governance of tourism and sustainability // Journal of Sustainable Tourism*. – 2011. – Vol. 19, No. 4–5.

7 United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). *Sustainable Tourism for Development Guidebook*. – Madrid: UNWTO, 2021

8 Mamatqulova, D. *Yashil turizm infratuzilmasini yaratishning innovatsion yo'nalishlari // Iqtisodiyot va Innovatsiyalar*. – 2022. – №4. – B. 72–78.

9 United Nations Environment Programme & UNWTO. *Making Tourism More Sustainable: A Guide for Policy Makers*. – Madrid: UNWTO, 2018.

- The economic benefits of sustainable tourism are also significant: it positively impacts the local economy and enhances the competitiveness of the tourism sector.
- Furthermore, the core principles of green tourism - preserving natural and cultural heritage, minimizing the environmental impact of tourism services, and safeguarding the interests of local communities - position it as a strategic direction for future tourism policy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article was written using the literature review method. The study applied the following sources and approach:

- The official tourism and conservation policies of selected countries were analyzed, including Costa Rica, Slovenia's national "Slovenia Green" program and Green Scheme, Bhutan's "High Value, Low Volume" approach, New Zealand's "Tiaki Promise," and hotel certification systems in Germany (GreenSign).
- For each foreign experience, elements such as policy, financing, certification, public participation, marketing, and infrastructure were examined, and their applicability to the context of Uzbekistan was assessed.
- Recommendations for applying the experiences of foreign countries were summarized: which mechanisms can be directly transferred, which need to be adapted, and which require significant modification to suit Uzbekistan's conditions.

Below, the selected foreign experiences, their key components, and the identified directions for adaptation to Uzbekistan are presented.

Costa Rica has developed ecotourism at the national level, based on biodiversity conservation and environmental protection. The country has promoted tourism through nature preservation and its national park system, such as the National Conservation System. A significant portion of the land is designated as protected areas, and tourism revenue is directed toward conservation efforts. Additionally, incentives are provided for community projects and ecological tourism businesses¹⁰.

Uzbekistan has the potential to host internationally significant natural parks, such as those in Chorvoq, Bukhara, and the Khorezm region, as well as the Zarafshan mountain ranges, among others. Lessons from Costa Rica include strengthening the management of national parks and tourist zones, allocating a portion of tourism revenue to dedicated conservation funds, and involving local communities in generating income.

Slovenia has implemented a national "Green Scheme" brand and comprehensive certification system. The country developed the "Slovenia Green" brand nationwide, encouraging regions and service providers to align with the national green tourism direction. Many tourist destinations and service providers have received the Slovenia Green certification, supporting the creation of a centralized and interconnected national strategy¹¹.

The Slovenian model can serve as a basis for introducing a national centralized certification and branding strategy in Uzbekistan, such as an "Uzbekistan Green" initiative. In this framework, local tourist regions—for example, Samarkand with its historical cities, and the Fergana Valley with its mountain and rural ecotourism—would be classified as tourist brands, with sustainability standards developed specifically for them.

Bhutan follows the "High Value, Low Volume" tourism policy. The country develops tourism in a targeted and controlled manner, selecting visitors through high fees (daily taxes or weekly tariffs) to ensure the protection of the environment and cultural heritage. This approach limits tourist flows while maximizing the effectiveness of tourism-generated revenue¹².

Uzbekistan currently offers rapid accessibility and competitive pricing for many tourist regions. While the Bhutan model cannot be fully transferred due to differences in geopolitical location, distance, and infrastructure, its concept of "targeted segmentation" should be studied. This could involve attracting high-value tourists through premium tourism packages, cultural-travel experiences, and eco-routes. As a practical measure, certain tourist destinations could implement management limits and introduce premium fees for additional services.

New Zealand — The "Tiaki Promise" and national responsibility campaign encourage visitors to respect nature and local culture. Through this initiative, New Zealand promotes awareness and communication, as well as responsible behavior during tour operations. Additionally, national strategies in New Zealand aim to minimize the environmental and social impacts of tourism¹³.

The national ethics campaign modeled on New Zealand's "Tiaki Promise" can be implemented in Uzbekistan at the national or regional level—for example, through a "Uzbek Tourist and Guest: Respect Nature and Culture" initiative. This would educate visitors on environmental protection, waste reduction, and adherence to cultural norms.

¹⁰ <https://www.visitcostarica.com/sustainability>

¹¹ <https://www.slovenia.info/en/business/green-scheme-of-slovenian-tourism>

¹² <https://www.bhutanmajestictravel.com/travel-information/tourism-policy>

¹³ <https://www.tourismnewzealand.com/partner-with-us/tiaki>

Germany (and Europe) — Applying systems like Green Sign in the hotel industry, Germany and other European countries have various certification programs for hotels and tourist facilities, including Green Sign, EU Ecolabel, and programs aligned with the Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC) standards. Through certification, service providers demonstrate environmental efficiency, energy and water conservation, waste management, and collaboration with local communities. Introducing a national or regional certification system for hotels and tourism services in Uzbekistan would be a crucial step in promoting green practices and meeting international standards. Certification also provides additional marketing opportunities for hotels and builds investor confidence¹⁴.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Based on the above findings, the following conclusions and recommendations are proposed for the development of green tourism in Uzbekistan:

A national brand, similar to Slovenia's "Slovenia Green," would facilitate the creation of a single, recognized center for sustainability within the country. In Uzbekistan, a comparable "Uzbekistan Green" model could be developed, including national regulations, standards, a list of designated green destinations, and a certification mechanism. This would serve as a mark of trust for tourists and operators and could be leveraged in marketing efforts¹⁵.

Practical Steps:

- Develop national green standards through the Ministry of Tourism or a dedicated agency.
- Establish a certification authority or develop a national system aligned with international standards (GSTC).
- Select pilot regions and conduct trials (for example, the Samarkand region: cultural heritage + green management).

In Costa Rica, designated protected areas and the conservation system are funded in part by tourism revenues, which are allocated for environmental protection. In Uzbekistan, a similar "eco-fund" system could be implemented for large natural areas such as national parks and biosphere reserves. This fund would support environmental restoration, trail and infrastructure maintenance, and the financing of local community projects.

Practical Steps:

- Introduce special fees for access to parks and reserves, directing them directly to the conservation fund.
- Develop a mechanism for distributing revenue to local communities, ensuring socio-economic benefits.

While Bhutan's model may not be fully transferable everywhere, its core idea—attracting a limited number of high-spending, quality-focused tourists—can be adapted to Uzbekistan, particularly for historical cities and exclusive cultural packages. Uzbekistan can increase the value per tourist through premium experiences (cultural festivals, personal curators, special gastronomic events), thereby boosting revenue without overburdening the environment.

Practical Steps:

- Develop premium packages and "slow tourism" routes.
- Manage costs according to visitors' payment capacity (e.g., special fees or bundled service packages).

Based on the New Zealand example, national campaigns educate tourists to behave responsibly. In the context of Uzbekistan, it is important to implement a national code of ethics (e.g., respect for historical buildings, waste reduction, adherence to cultural norms) alongside a broad information and communication campaign.

Practical Steps:

- Provide tourists with concise "Rules and Recommendations" through entry cards, websites, and information at airports and stations.
- Implement training programs for leading tour operators and guides.

In Germany and Europe, certifications encourage hotels and tour operators to adopt green practices. Uzbekistan can similarly incentivize the private sector through tax benefits, grants, or loans to promote energy efficiency, waste reduction, and the implementation of green infrastructure¹⁶. Practical Measures:

- Introduce green loans and subsidy schemes (e.g., for installing solar panels or energy-efficient lighting).
- Provide marketing support and opportunities to participate in international events for entities that receive certification.

14 Karimov M, Okmullaev R, Marty P, Saidmamatov O. Tourism Sustainability in Uzbekistan: Challenges and Opportunities Along the Silk Road. *Economies*. 2025; 13(9):250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies13090250>

15 <https://www.slovenia.info/en/business/green-scheme-of-slovenian-tourism>

16 <https://germany.controlunion.com/en/certification-program/greensign-certification>

In Costa Rica and other countries, local communities are key stakeholders in the social and economic benefits of tourism. In Uzbekistan, sustainability can be enhanced by economically involving communities in areas such as handicrafts, agro-tourism, and homestays.

Practical Steps:

- Support local entrepreneurship through microloans, education, and marketing assistance.
- Involve local communities in management and decision-making processes.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Green Tourism is a sustainable form of tourism aimed at generating positive outcomes for local communities and economies without causing harm to nature and ecological systems. The main principles of green tourism include:

- Rational use of water, energy, and other resources;
- Maintaining ecological and economic sustainability;
- Preserving natural and cultural heritage for future generations;
- Ensuring collaboration between local communities and government in tourism management;
- Implementing innovative technologies and reducing waste.

Thus, green tourism is viewed as an integrated tourism concept that delivers not only ecological but also economic and social benefits.

Foreign experiences indicate that the successful development of green tourism requires the integration of several key elements: a national strategy and brand, a clear certification mechanism, financial instruments aimed at environmental management, engagement of local communities, and the promotion of responsible behavior among tourists. The main recommendations for Uzbekistan are:

1. Develop a national “Uzbekistan Green” strategy — defining certification, branding, and regional roles.
2. Establish a nature conservation fund — implementing entry fees for national parks and protected areas with clear allocation of revenues.
3. Apply targeted segmentation — attract high-value tourists through premium and thematic packages (cultural, agro-, and eco-tourism).
4. Launch a national ethics campaign — educate tourists and service providers to act with respect toward the environment.
5. Implement certification and financial incentives — encourage the private sector to invest in green infrastructure.
6. Support local communities — channel revenues to the local level and involve communities in decision-making processes.

Effective collaboration between the government, private sector, and civil society is essential to implement these initiatives. International experiences show that a systematic approach—integrating strategy, financing, education, and marketing—yields the best results, rather than a one-sided policy.

For the future, it is recommended to:

- Test experimental certification and financing models in several pilot regions of Uzbekistan.
- Assess social impacts through surveys of tourists and local communities.
- Conduct economic analyses to evaluate how effectively tourism revenues are allocated for environmental protection.

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